

CHESS SETUP: STEP 3

CHESS SETUP coming into tangible actions

Welcome to our 3rd newsletter, we wish you a pleasant reading

The European project investigating buildings' energy self-sufficiency

CSU General conference: thanks to all of you!

On November 15th was held CHESS SETUP's General Conference at the Smart City Expo World Congress in Barcelona.

It was a great opportunity to disseminate the first project achievements in front of an audience of more than 50 people. The pilots had also the chance to introduce themselves and contrast their first outcomes.

We would like to warmly thank the Provincial Government of Barcelona and Sant Cugat City Council for hosting us.

Visit of "Ecoedifici"

The consortium gathered and worked during one day at Lavola's pilot located in Manlleu where was held the 4th CHESS SETUP meeting. The company introduced its plans to accommodate their new PV panels on their headquarters' (named Ecoedifici) rooftop.

Another element of the installation, the compressor from the heat pump, was just arriving from Ulster University, and will be added to the whole system soon.

Other pilots translated into concrete actions

Sant Cugat City Council succeeded in finalising an installation suitable to its sport center. Bound by public tendering processes, works must end by November 2018.

In Corby, work is about to start, and the first ecohomes must be built by Spring 2018.

CSU at NZEB Congress

On December 13th and 14th will be held the Spanish Near Zero Emission Building Congress (EECN in Spanish) in Madrid. The fair highlights initiatives reducing energy needs, and upgrading health and comfort levels in the building sector. Since public buildings must meet NZEB requirements by 2018, and by 2020 for all new buildings, the theme is quite a key theme!

CHESS SETUP project has been selected through the call for abstract, and you will find its concept and first achievements in the Book of abstract.

The 12th of December, isn't a simple anniversary date. It's a day for action.

One planet Summit

Two years after COP21, Paris hosts another world event dedicated to finding concrete solutions to "make our planet great again". The credo? There is no plan(et) B! The event focuses on tangible actions: how to finance climate action, how to green finance, how to accelerate local action, etc. Heads of State, officials, but also citizens and companies are invited at this meeting organized by France, the UN and the World Bank Group.

Towards energy emission targets more ambitious?

The European Parliament proposed in a resolution to rise energy consumption reduction objectives from 30% to 40% by 2030. MEPs also agreed a minimum of 35% of all energy consumed in the EU would need to come from renewable sources.

Click [here](#) for more info.

"54 million Europeans cannot afford to heat their homes in winter and about the same number are either facing energy debts or living in deteriorated dwellings."

[BUILD UP](#), The European portal for Energy Efficiency in Buildings

Comparte vía:

<http://www.chess-setup.net>